

***Ex Situ* Diversity of *Sorghum bicolor* (L.) moench Collections and Derived Wide Crosses (sorghum x maize) Based on DArTSeq Markers**

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Abstract

Sorghum is an important crop in sub-Saharan Africa. However, despite its importance, sorghum continues to have limited research attention and priority and is categorised as one of the Neglected and Underutilised Species. Paucity of current information on genetic diversity and structure of sorghum accessions being cultivated, improved, introduced, and or conserved across east and southern Africa remains limiting. Ex situ genetic diversity and population structure for 177 sorghum accessions from diverse sources was studied using high throughput Diversity Array Technology markers. A total of 30,030 SilicoDArT markers and 15,220 DArTseq SNP markers were generated with over 90% call rate and 95% reproducibility. DArTseq SNP markers had an average polymorphic information content of 0.21 indicating the discriminatory power of DArTSeq markers. Genetic relationships estimated using discriminant analysis of principal components and ancestry coefficients revealed four major clusters with eight subclusters. Observed heterozygosity was lower than the expected heterozygosity across populations with a mean inbreeding coefficient (F_{IS}) of 0.82. Analysis of molecular variance found 83% of the variation to be attributed to within-population variance. A high divergence ($F_{ST} = 0.16$) obtained from AMOVA suggests high genetic differentiation among populations. Genetic diversity indices Shannon-wiener index (H) (3.37 – 3.95), Stoddard and Taylor index (G) (29 – 52) and Simpson's index (λ - Lambda) (0.90 -0.99) were high across populations. Nei's unbiased gene diversity ranged from 0.13 - 0.23. The results suggest a high differentiation among sorghum accessions under study. Implications with respect to insights to guide identification, selection and testing of plant genetic resources for food and agriculture with unique genes and traits to address demand-led crop improvement and market needs, conservation, and deployment in farmer fields are shared.

Introduction

Sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench), the fifth most important cereal globally is a staple for more than 500 million people living in developing countries (Pennisi, 2009). Sorghum is a versatile crop with a C4 photosynthetic pathway enabling it exhibit water use efficiency and resilience to environmental shocks such as drought and heat stress. Sorghum adapts well to diverse marginal environments with minimal inputs and contributes to food security for millions of farm families in arid and semi-arid regions. However, this important attribute is threatened by an increasing loss of genetic diversity which supports diversification, re-introduction and or development of new locally adapted climate resilient lines. Variability in climate and human activity such as stringent selection on-farm, crop improvement programs, and large monocultures contribute in part to diminishing sorghum genetic diversity. This impacts available sorghum genetic resources for use directly as varieties or in the development of newly adapted germplasm.

Sorghum genetic resources available in farmer fields, gene bank collections, introductions, elite released cultivars and wild progenitors hold immense genetic variation (Upadhyaya et al., 2016). However, there remains paucity of information on existing genetic variation of sorghum germplasm available in east and southern Africa (ESA) to influence deployment of improved and adapted climate resilient genetic resources or that targeted for crop improvement. Studies on characterizing sorghum using a diverse array of molecular markers have been reported (Motlhaodi et al., 2017; Ramu et al., 2013; Ruiz-Chután et al., 2019; Cuevas & Prom, 2020; Menamo et al., 2021; Yahaya et al., 2023). The advent of Diversity Array Technology (DArT) revolutionized genetic diversity studies and genome-wide characterization of germplasm without the need for prior sequence information (Sansaloni et al., 2011). This study aimed to determine the existing genetic diversity of sorghum genetic resources in ESA and contribute to making available local, collected, introduced and novel wide cross (sorghum x maize) (Bombom and Ovuga, 2015) germplasm to support uptake, adoption, conservation, and sustainable use. We envisage these results will contribute to enabling farmers and end-users around the world to use and conserve adapted varieties leading to increased productivity, on-farm incomes, increased availability of nutrient-rich food, reduced adverse impacts to the environment, and enhanced resilience to production shocks as well as biodiversity for food security safeguarded for the future.

Materials and methods

Germplasm

A total of 177 sorghum accessions comprising local collections, gene bank accessions, introductions, elite commercial lines, and novel wide crosses (sorghum x maize) (Bombom and Ovuga, 2015) were used in this study (Supplementary Table S1). The sources from which sorghum germplasm were accessed include the National Agricultural Research Organisation (NARO)-Plant Genetic Resource Center (PGRC) gene bank, Entebbe, Uganda and NARO constituent institutes the National Livestock Resources Research Institute (NaLIRRI); National Semi-Arid Resources Research Institute (NaSARRI); and Abi Zonal Agricultural Research and Development Institute (AbiZARDI); Genetic Resources and Biotechnology Institute (GRBI)

gene bank, Harare, Zimbabwe; International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-arid Tropics (ICRISAT), gene bank Matopos, Zimbabwe; and Bomvitae Agro Industries Limited (BAIL), Kampala, Uganda.

Genotyping-by-Sequencing (GBS)

Leaf samples were collected from 177 sorghum genotypes, preserved using silica gel (silicon dioxide) in a desiccator, and shipped to SEQART AFRICA (International Livestock Research Institute, Nairobi, Kenya) for genotype by sequencing ((Sansaloni et al., 2011; Mufumbo *et al.*, 2023). Two DArTseq marker types were scored: SilicoDArT markers and SNP markers as present (1) or absent (0). ‘-’ for failure to score and 1/1 as heterozygotes (presence for both alleles). Subsequently, SilicoDArT markers and SNP markers were identified and called using sorghum reference genome v3.1.1, NCBI taxonomy ID: 4558 (McCormick et al., 2018).

DArTSeq SNP and SilicoDArT marker analysis

DArTSeq SNP and SilicoDArT marker quality were analyzed based on minor allele frequency, call rate (%), polymorphic information content (PIC), and reproducibility (%) using DArTView software (<https://software.kddart.com/kdxplore/dartview/>). Genetic richness, diversity and evenness parameters such as observed heterozygosity (H_o), expected heterozygosity (uH_e), pairwise differentiation between populations (F_{ST}), average inbreeding coefficient (F_{IS}), Nei’s unbiased gene diversity, Shannon index, evenness and index of association were calculated using DArTR (Gruber *et al.*, 2018) and Poppr package version 2.9.3 (Kamvar *et al.*, 2014) for R software (The R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna: <https://www.R-project.org/>). Population differentiation and gene flow were assessed using analysis of molecular variance (AMOVA) and coefficient of genetic differentiation among populations (PhiPT) using *poppr.amova* and *randtest* functions of poppr package respectively.

Population structure and genetic relationships

Population structure and genetic relationship were analyzed as described by Kaweesi et al. (2023). Structure of the sorghum germplasm was assessed based on ancestry coefficients and the number of ancestry populations using the R package, LEA version 3.8.0 (Frichot & François, 2015). Runs of sparse non-negative matrix factorization (sNMF) were performed for values of the number of clusters set at $K=2-10$. The function *snnmf* was also used to compute and plot an entropy criterion curve. The minimum cross-entropy value was selected as the possible number of ancestral populations or clusters that best explain the genotypic data (Alexander & Lange, 2011; Frichot *et al.*, 2014). A discriminant analysis of principal components (DAPC) was done to confirm the results using *find.clusters* and *dapc* functions of *DartR* R package version 2.0.4. The lowest Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) value was used to infer the optimal number of genetic clusters (K) to describe the genetic data (Figure S1). Each sorghum genotype was assigned to a given cluster based on membership probabilities. DArT trimmed sequences for each genotype were concatenated using *gl2fasta* function in *dartR* to generate a single composite haplotype in fasta format. The heterogeneous

state was resolved by randomly assigning one or another SNP variant to an individual. The composite haplotype fasta file was re-aligned and used in Molecular Evolutionary Genetics Analysis software (MEGA) version 11 (Tamura *et al.*, 2021) to generate a neighbor-joining tree using default parameters. Genetic relationships between sorghum accessions were visualized using the Neighbour-Joining method, implemented in MEGA v11. To estimate pairwise relatedness, the genetic distances among sorghum accessions were analyzed based on Prevosti's absolute genetic distance (Prevosti *et al.*, 1975) using *prevosti.dist* function in *poppr* R package.

Results

Quality of DArTseq markers

Genotyping 177 sorghum accessions yielded 30,030 SilicoDArT markers and 15,220 DArTseq SNP markers. SilicoDArT markers had a polymorphic information content (PIC) of 0.22, with a call rate ranging from 0.803 to 1.00 and a mean call rate of 0.92. A proportion (56.5%) of these SilicoDArT markers had a call rate and reproducibility above 0.9 and 0.95 respectively. DArTseq-based SNP markers had a minor allele frequency of 0.15, a polymorphic information content (PIC) of 0.21, and a call rate of 0.88. Among the SNP markers, 9445 markers had a call rate and reproducibility above 0.90 and 0.95 respectively. Due to the dominant nature of SilicoDArT markers, they were not considered for downstream analysis in this study.

Genetic Relationships and Population Structure

The population structure for 177 sorghum accessions was estimated using DAPC and ancestry coefficients implemented in LEA software. Results from DAPC revealed four major clusters with eight subclusters (Figure 1). A list of accessions within each of the eight subclusters is presented in Table S2.

Figure 1: Discriminant analysis of principal components (DAPC) scatter plot showing dispersion of different clusters based on DArTSeq SNP markers. Numbers show distribution of clusters in different quadrants.

Within cluster 1, are subclusters 2 and 4 comprising 32.2% (56 accessions) of the collection (Figure 1). Subcluster 2 comprised mainly landraces obtained from NARO under the Plant Genetic Resources Center (PGRC) gene bank and farmer fields during collection missions. Subcluster 4 comprised wide cross progenitors obtained from BAIL in Uganda, which clustered with two commercial lines Taurus and Temani-16H. Cluster 2 comprised only subcluster 8 with 5.2% of the population (9 accessions) including landraces and breeding lines from ICRISAT and GRBI gene banks in Zimbabwe. Cluster 3 comprised 4 subclusters including subcluster(s) 1, 3, 5, and 6, accounting for 39.6% (69 accessions) of the total population. This is the largest cluster and includes wide cross progenitors from BAIL, landraces, and breeding accessions from ICRISAT, GRBI, and NARO-PGRC gene banks. Cluster 4 comprised only subcluster 7 with 23% (40 accessions) of the population predominantly landraces and breeding lines from ICRISAT and GRBI gene banks in Zimbabwe (Figure 1, Table S2). Similar to the results from DAPC, a heatmap based on DArTSeq SNP markers revealed four major clusters and eight subclusters (Figure 2). Genetic distance among populations represented by the neighbor-joining phylogenetic tree distinctly clustered the 177 accessions into eight subclusters (Figure 3) corroborating the results revealed by DAPC (Figure 1) and Heatmap (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Heatmap based on DArTSeq SNP markers showing genotypic similarity among four major clusters and associated eight subclusters for sorghum accessions from east and southern Africa.

Figure 3: Neighbor-Joining Clustering based on DArTSeq SNP markers for sorghum accessions from east and southern Africa.

Cluster 2 (comprising subcluster 8) and cluster 4 (comprising subcluster 7) formed unique clades consisting of accessions from ICRISAT and GRBI gene banks in Zimbabwe classified as landraces, breeding lines, and commercial line(s) (Figure 3). Cluster 1 had two distinct clades comprising subclusters 2 and 4. Subcluster 2 consisted of landrace accessions from the NARO-PGRC gene bank, and local collections from farmer fields (Lawera and Abi series), with seven (7) wide cross progenitors (ABJ2233_T23, Sb3038, 152(6), 132(5), 138, Sb3041_15, 126(3)) interspersed within this clade. Subcluster 4 presented as a unique clade from BAIL comprising only wide cross (sorghum x maize) progenitors. However, two commercial lines – Taurus and Temani-16H, clustered within this clade (Figure 3). Cluster 3 comprised of 4 admixed clades consisting of accessions from ICRISAT and GRBI gene banks in Zimbabwe, local collections and commercial lines from NARO-AbiZARDI/ NaSARRI/ PGRC, breeding lines and wide cross progenitors obtained from BAIL in Uganda (Figure 3). The ancestry matrix obtained from LEA similarly suggests eight populations with an optimal value $K = 8$ (Figure S1). All populations were admixed, except cluster 1 which had unique individuals that showed no admixture such as 91 (34_SS), 102 (ABJ 2234), and 140 (ABJ 2406) (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Population structure of 177 sorghum accessions from east and southern Africa based on DArTSeq SNP markers.

Figure 5: Assessment of heterozygosity within different sorghum populations from ESA. Observed heterozygosity (H_o), expected heterozygosity (uHe) and inbreeding coefficient (F_{IS}).

Genetic Diversity Parameters

Genetic diversity parameters based on DArTseq SNP markers for 177 sorghum accessions revealed low overall observed genetic diversity (0.21) and heterozygosity (0.03). Observed heterozygosity (H_o) was lower than the expected heterozygosity (uHe) across populations

(Figure 5). The u_{He} was highest in collections from the GRBI gene bank (0.23) and lowest among collections from BAIL (0.14) (Figure 5). A mean inbreeding coefficient (F_{IS}) of 0.82 was observed in this study (Table 1). Accessions from the GRBI gene bank in Zimbabwe had the highest F_{IS} values while wide crosses from BAIL exhibited the lowest F_{IS} (Figure 5).

Analysis of molecular variance (AMOVA) showed that 83% of the variance was found within populations and 17% between populations (Table 1). A high F_{st} (0.16) was obtained from AMOVA with a coefficient of genetic differentiation among populations (Φ_{PT}) of 0.17 and gene flow (N_m) of 1.19. Pairwise genetic distances ranged from 0.06 between accessions from ICRISAT and GRBI gene banks to 0.33 between accessions from ICRISAT and NARO gene banks (Table 2). All accessions exhibited high genetic richness with high multilocus genotypes ranging from 38-56 (Table 3). Genetic diversity indices Shannon-wiener index (H) (3.64 – 4.03), Stoddard and Taylor index (G) (38 – 56) and Simpson's index (λ - Lambda) (0.97 -0.98) were high across clusters. Nei's unbiased gene diversity ranged from 0.14 - 0.23 with the wide cross populations exhibiting the highest genetic diversity indices – 4.03, 56, and 0.982 for the H , G , and λ respectively (Table 3).

Table 1 Analysis of molecular variance for genetic differentiation among and within clusters of sorghum accessions from ESA

	df	SS	MS	Sigma	% Var.	P-value	Fstat.
Between population	3	1.60	0.38	0.01	17	0.01	$F_{ST} = 0.16$
Within population	173	6.64	0.04	0.04	83		$F_{IS} = 0.82$
Total	176	7.79	0.04	0.05	100		

Φ_{PT} – Coefficient of genetic differentiation among accession populations = 0.172; Gene flow (N_m) = 1.19; df = degrees of freedom; SS = sum of squared observations; MS = mean of squared observations; % Var. = percentage of total variance; overall observed genetic diversity (H_t) = 0.21

Table 2: Pairwise F_{ST} values between sorghum populations from Uganda and Zimbabwe

	NARO	GRBI	BAIL	ICRISAT
NARO	0.00			
GRBI	0.19	0.00		
BAIL	0.11	0.18	0.00	
ICRISAT	0.33	0.06	0.31	0.00

Table 3: Genetic richness and diversity of sorghum accession from ESA

Population	N	MLG	eMLG	SE	H	G	λ	Hexp
NARO	38	38	38	0.00e+00	3.64	38	0.974	0.15
GRBI	38	38	38	0.00e+00	3.64	38	0.974	0.23
BAIL	56	56	38	0.00e+00	4.03	56	0.982	0.14
ICRISAT	45	45	38	0.00e+00	3.81	45	0.978	0.19
Total	177	177	38	0.00e+00	5.18	177	0.994	0.21

N – Number of individuals observed, MLG – Number of multilocus genotypes, eMLG – the number of MLG at the smallest sample size ≥ 10 based on rarefaction, SE – Standard error based on eMLG, H – Shannon-wiener index of MLG diversity, G – Stoddard and Taylor's index of MLG diversity, λ (Lambda) – Simpson's index, Hexp – Nei's unbiased gene diversity.

Discussion

Insights into genetic diversity and structure of any plant species is useful to guide effective collection missions, conservation and management – in situ and ex situ, trait improvements and utilization of plant genetic resources for food and agriculture (PGRFA). A major challenge, however, is the paucity of information on available genetic diversity in collections within national agricultural research systems (NARS) at any given time. This subsequently impacts conservation and utilization initiatives. Sorghum belongs to a diverse group of cereal crops in sub-Saharan Africa referred to as Millets, important globally for their potential to contribute to food security, nutrition, health, resilience, and adaptation to climate change (Bombom et al., 2023). However, limited attention and priority has been paid to sorghum and millets in general, resulting in their classification as orphaned or neglected underutilized species (NUS). Existing knowledge on available diversity and structure of sorghum collections in east and southern Africa is based on traditional knowledge, morphological characterization, and limited recent genetic studies on small populations (Mufumbo et al., 2023). To broaden our understanding of the nature of sorghum genetic resources available in the region, this study utilized collections from national and international gene banks and private sector research partners. The collections, comprised accessions of diverse biological status including landraces, local collections from farmer fields, breeding lines, commercial lines, and wide crosses generated from hybridisation between sorghum and maize (Bombom and Ovuga, 2015).

DArTseq SNP markers were used to elucidate genetic diversity and population structure of sorghum accessions from diverse sources in ESA specifically, Uganda and Zimbabwe. The average polymorphic information content (0.21) obtained with DArTSeq SNP markers in this study was moderate and similar to that reported in other studies on sorghum - 0.24 (Enyew et al., 2022), 0.26 (Yahaya et al., 2023) and 0.21 in macadamia (Alam et al., 2018). Based on these and previous studies, our results further iterate the informativeness and discriminatory ability of DArTSeq SNP markers in genetic diversity studies. Four major clusters and 8 subclusters were observed as shown by DAPC, Heatmap, and phylogenetic tree visualizations (Figure 1-4). Clusters 2 and 4 comprised one subcluster each that formed unique clades – that is, subcluster 8 and 7 respectively (Table S2, Figure 1-4). Both subclusters 8 and 7 contained within clusters 2 and 4 respectively were dominated by breeding lines and landrace accessions obtained from ICRISAT and GRBI in Zimbabwe; the former holding representation from different parts of the world as sources of origin (Table S1). Two unique subclusters or clades – 2 and 4 were observed within cluster 1 (Table S2, Figure 1-4). Clade 2 comprised of landrace accessions from the national gene bank (NARO-PGRC) and farmer collections in Uganda interspersed with wide cross progenitors (Figure 3, Table S2). Clade 4 comprised majorly wide cross progenitors from BAIL in Uganda. Cluster 3 was admixed comprising four subclusters – 1, 3, 5, and 6. Of interest within cluster 3 is subcluster 1 where wide cross progenitors clustered together with their parents (Figure 3). The association of wide crosses and its relationship with accessions from diverse sources may be attributed to speciation and or evolution events. Wide crosses offer the potential for gene transfer between species and or genera, creation of novel genetic variation including new character traits absent in parents, haploid induction and doubled haploids, and the development of novel crop species (Zenktele & Nitzsche 1984). Unpublished data on intergeneric hybridisation of sorghum with maize suggests wide cross

progenitors used in this study as homoploid hybrids with the ability to restore racial diversity of sorghum from a single cross. This might explain the observed relationships between wide cross progenitors with the landraces and other accessions of different biological status in this study (Table S1, Table S2, Figure 1-4).

Genetic variation as revealed by AMOVA suggests within population variation (83%) to be the main contributing factor for the total variation observed in the accessions under study. Only 17% was attributed to genetic differences between populations. Similar observations have been reported for sorghum and other crops studied using DArTSeq SNP markers (Adugna, 2014; Afolayan et al., 2019). Complementary with the AMOVA results, was a high mean coefficient of inbreeding ($F_{IS}=0.82$). The results further indicated that observed heterozygosity (H_o) was lower than expected heterozygosity (uH_e) for all populations suggesting inbreeding within populations. Genetic differentiation ($F_{ST} = 0.16$) was high among populations. Genetic distances as depicted by F_{ST} values between populations exhibited a range (0.06 – 0.33) suggesting moderate to high genetic differentiation between populations in this study. The genetic distance between ICRISAT and GRBI gene banks in Zimbabwe was low ($F_{ST} = 0.06$). The observed result suggests sharing of genetic materials, especially of local land race accessions between the national gene bank GRBI in Zimbabwe and ICRISAT gene bank in Matopos. The high genetic distance ($F_{ST} = 0.33$) between ICRISAT and NARO populations is indicative of the distinctness of the gene pools held at the respective gene banks – biologically diverse global collections at ICRISAT versus local land race accessions and collections at NARO. This, coupled with geographical isolation and adaptation to environment overtime might contribute to the observed genetic distances between international and national gene bank accessions. Between ICRISAT and BAIL, the high genetic differentiation observed might be attributed to geographic isolation of genetic resources with limited improvement on select accessions since their collection. The wide crosses from BAIL on the other hand are a result of hybridization between two genera – *Sorghum* and *Zea* producing fertile offspring with speciation events still ongoing. The gene flow (Nm) value of 1.19 suggests there is a genetic exchange between populations attributed to crop improvement efforts, safety duplication and or conservation to safeguard PGRFA. This is evidenced by the different sources of germplasm listed in Table S1 that are shared between the international gene bank at ICRISAT and partners including NARO, GBRI and other global institutions. All accessions had high genetic richness with genetic diversity indices Shannon-wiener index, Stoddard and Taylor index and Simpson's index (λ - Lambda) observed to be high across clusters. The high genetic indices observed with wide crosses suggests speciation events among the progenitors stemming from hybridization of the genera, *Sorghum* and *Zea*.

Conclusion and future perspectives

Conservation and management of plant genetic resources for food and agriculture (PGRFA) is crucial towards contributing to smallholder farmers' access and utilization of adapted germplasm “*leading to increased productivity and on-farm incomes, increased availability of*

nutrient-rich food, reduced adverse impacts to the environment, and enhanced resilience to production shocks. And that: Biodiversity for food security is safeguarded for the future”.

This is a goal iterated by the Secretariat of the International Treaty for Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture (ITPGRFA) of the Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO) of the United Nations (UN). With diverse pressures from climate change among a myriad of challenges, climate vulnerability poses significant threats to agriculture globally. This in effect contributes to the emergence and re-emergence of pests and diseases, extremes of weather events such as floods or droughts, and unpredictable harvests. To enable farmers, adapt and become resilient, developing, and availing appropriate technologies and knowledge to communities that suit their local contexts and needs at farm level is imperative. To achieve this, it is noteworthy that appropriate genes and associated traits in accessions are identified, selected, and tested well ahead of the climate curve. This study aimed to gain insights into the available genetic diversity and structure of sorghum accessions currently available in east and southern Africa as a first step in light of increasing climate variability.

Genetic differentiation ranged from moderate to high among the populations under study. However, oftentimes, genetic studies and morphological characterization only provide insightful information for stakeholders in the scientific community with conservation and crop improvement interests. Interaction with stakeholders in industry and direct beneficiaries or users such as smallholder farmers is given limited attention. As such, a number of varieties get released into the public domain but have low or no uptake, adoption, use and subsequently limited impact on farming communities. To contribute to impact, it is imperative we go a step further to characterise and understand diversity by function. This will facilitate selection, conservation and management and crop improvement efforts for varieties and or plant genetic resources with targeted niche market segments and industrial applications. This can be achieved using available modern tools and technologies in crop improvement to identify, select, and test PGRFA possessing unique genes and traits to facilitate use beyond research, conservation and management following demand-led principles. The different unique populations especially the wide crosses in this study provide an important starting point. New knowledge and insights from this study and planned characterisation work on diversity by function of sorghum accessions will guide deployment in farmer fields or use as bridging species in crop improvement programs in developing climate-resilient sorghum varieties.

Author contribution

A.B. conceived the idea; A.B. and M.M. contributed genetic material; T.K. performed data analysis; A.B., E.O., P.A. and M.M. reviewed the manuscript; A.B. acquired funding; All co-authors contributed to preparation and development of the final manuscript.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Table S1: List of sorghum germplasm genotyped with DArTSeq Markers

	Entry Code	Accession Code	Holding Country	Source Institute	Biological Status	Country of origin
1	UNGB1576	UNGB1576	Uganda	NARO-PGRC	Landrace	Entebbe, Uganda
2	UNGB2674	UNGB2674	Uganda	NARO-PGRC	Landrace	Entebbe, Uganda
3	UNGB2884	UNGB2884	Uganda	NARO-PGRC	Landrace	Entebbe, Uganda
4	UNGB2986	UNGB2986	Uganda	NARO-PGRC	Landrace	Entebbe, Uganda
5	UNGB1574	UNGB1574	Uganda	NARO-PGRC	Landrace	Entebbe, Uganda
6	UNGB2894	UNGB2894	Uganda	NARO-PGRC	Landrace	Entebbe, Uganda
7	UNGB2744	UNGB2744	Uganda	NARO-PGRC	Landrace	Entebbe, Uganda
8	UNGB115	UNGB115	Uganda	NARO-PGRC	Landrace	Entebbe, Uganda
9	UNGB98	UNGB98	Uganda	NARO-PGRC	Landrace	Entebbe, Uganda
10	UNGB2314	UNGB2314	Uganda	NARO-PGRC	Landrace	Entebbe, Uganda
11	UNGB2890	UNGB2890	Uganda	NARO-PGRC	Landrace	Entebbe, Uganda
12	UNGB3015	UNGB3015	Uganda	NARO-PGRC	Landrace	Entebbe, Uganda
13	UNGB2866	UNGB2866	Uganda	NARO-PGRC	Landrace	Entebbe, Uganda
14	UNGB2888	UNGB2888	Uganda	NARO-PGRC	Landrace	Entebbe, Uganda
15	UNGB2830	UNGB2830	Uganda	NARO-PGRC	Landrace	Entebbe, Uganda
16	UNGB2796	UNGB2796	Uganda	NARO-PGRC	Landrace	Entebbe, Uganda
17	UNGB2901	UNGB2901	Uganda	NARO-PGRC	Landrace	Entebbe, Uganda
18	UNGB2898	UNGB2898	Uganda	NARO-PGRC	Landrace	Entebbe, Uganda
19	UNGB2318	UNGB2318	Uganda	NARO-PGRC	Landrace	Entebbe, Uganda
20	UNGB2777	UNGB2777	Uganda	NARO-PGRC	Landrace	Entebbe, Uganda
21	UNGB2688	UNGB2688	Uganda	NARO-PGRC	Landrace	Entebbe, Uganda
22	UNGB2730	UNGB2730	Uganda	NARO-PGRC	Landrace	Entebbe, Uganda
23	Lawera	Lawera	Uganda	NARO-NaLIRRI	Local collection	Kitgum, Uganda
24	Abi3	Abi3	Uganda	NARO-AbiZARDI	Local collection	Arua, Uganda
25	Abi13	Abi13	Uganda	NARO-AbiZARDI	Local collection	Arua, Uganda

26	Abi2	Abi2	Uganda	NARO-AbiZARDI	Local collection	Arua, Uganda
27	Abi9	Abi9	Uganda	NARO-AbiZARDI	Local collection	Arua, Uganda
28	Abi12	Abi12	Uganda	NARO-AbiZARDI	Local collection	Arua, Uganda
29	SESO3	SESO3	Uganda	NARO-NaSARRI	Commercial line	Serere, Uganda
30	NAROSORG2	IS8193	Uganda	NARO-NaSARRI	Commercial line	Nairobi, Kenya
31	NAROSORG3	IESV92043DL	Uganda	NARO-NaSARRI	Commercial line	Nairobi, Kenya
32	NAROSORG4	NAROSORG4	Uganda	NARO-NaSARRI	Commercial line	Serere, Uganda
33	ABJ_3	ABJ_3	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
34	225(19)	ABJ2005-2	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
35	RUS 001	ABJ 001	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
36	355(49)	ABJ2020-2	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
37	Sb3039	ABJ3039	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
38	263(54)	263(54)	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
39	Sb3036	ABJ3036	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
40	Sb3038	ABJ3038	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
41	ABJ2231-21	ABJ2231-21	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
42	126(3)	ABJ3031/AB3021	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
43	398	398	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
44	Sb3037	ABJ3037	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
45	ABJ2225-T15	ABJ2225-T15	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
46	ABJ2406	ABJ2406	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
47	ABJ2220-T10	ABJ2220-T10	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
48	ABJ2244-T39	ABJ2244-T39	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
49	ABJ2233-T23	ABJ2233-T23	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
50	R2X	R2X	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
51	331(40)	ABJ2020-2	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
52	396(68)	ABJ2075-4z	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda

53	304(29)	ABJ2005-2	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
54	385	385	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
55	379(60)G	ABJ2075-4z	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
56	SMT2056 #46	SMT2056 #46	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
57	362(54)B	ABJ2020-2	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
58	236(15)	ABJ2005-2	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
59	323(37)	ABJ2020-2	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
60	359(52)	ABJ2020-2	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
61	Sb3040	ABJ3040	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
62	343(45)W	ABJ2020-2	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
63	27/30_3036 P13	27/30_3036 P13	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
64	ABJ2234	ABJ2234	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
65	138	138	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
66	85	ABJ2075-4z	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
67	124B100	ABJ3029/ ABJ3007	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
68	Sb3045	ABJ3045	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
69	132(5)	ABJ3029/ ABJ3002	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
70	356	356	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
71	186(1)	186(1)	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
72	Sb3041	ABJ3041	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
73	Sb3041_15	ABJ3041_15	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
74	SMT2063#20	SMT2063#20	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
75	20x630_F3	20x630_F3	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
76	352	352	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
77	JK	ABJ2058	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
78	271(23)	ABJ2005-2	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
79	ABJ2405	ABJ2405	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda

80	388(65)	388(65)	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
81	381(61)	ABJ2075-4z	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
82	250(18)A	ABJ2005-2	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
83	Sb 39_5(x)108	ABJ3039-108	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
84	426(82)	426(82)	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
85	152(6)	ABJ2004-3	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
86	126(3)	ABJ3031/AB3021	Uganda	BAIL	Wide cross	Kampala, Uganda
87	Rus 008	Rus 008	Uganda	NARO-NaLIRRI	Pre-breeding line	Rostov, Russia
88	Sc sila	Sc sila	Uganda	NARO-NaLIRRI	Commercial line	-
89	PAC501	PAC501	Uganda	NARO-NaLIRRI	Commercial line	-
90	Taurus	Taurus	Uganda	NARO-NaLIRRI	Commercial line	-
91	Temani-16H	Temani-16H	Uganda	NARO-NaLIRRI	Commercial line	-
92	INDIA_23 SS	Sugar Graze	Uganda	NARO-NaLIRRI	Commercial line	India
93	G1	BTxARG-1	Uganda	BAIL	Breeding line	Texas A&M, USA
94	630B	BTx630	Uganda	BAIL	Breeding line	Texas A&M, USA
95	1_SS	IS 23843	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Landrace	Yemen
96	2_SS	IS 8891	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Landrace	Kisoko, Tororo, Uganda
97	3_SS	IS 10458	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Breeding line	Uganda
98	4_SS	IS 29440	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Landrace	Qacha's Nek, Lesotho
99	5_SS	IS 35533	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Landrace	Owambo, Namibia
100	6_SS	IS 10214	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Breeding line	France
101	7_SS	IS 6944	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Landrace	Nasir, Sudan
102	8_SS	IS 30047	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Landrace	Zimbabwe
103	9_SS	IS 30275	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Breeding line	Zimbabwe
104	10_SS	IS 3808	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Breeding line	Texas, USA
105	11_SS	IS 9388	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Breeding line	Gauteng, South Africa
106	12_SS	IS 29220	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Landrace	Mhulme, Swaziland

107	13_SS	IS 29903	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Landrace	Zimbabwe
108	14_SS	IS 23908	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Landrace	Yemen
109	15_SS	IS 9449	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Breeding line	Gauteng, South Africa
110	17_SS	IS 9405	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Landrace	Gauteng, South Africa
111	18_SS_LOCAL	IS 9410	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Land race	
112	19_SS	IS 29925	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Landrace	Hwange, Zimbabwe
113	20_SS	IS 13904	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Landrace	KZN, South Africa
114	21_SS	IS 24272	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Breeding line	Tanzania
116	22_SS	IS 13823	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Landrace	KZN, South Africa
117	24_SS	IS 29369	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Landrace	Berea, Lesotho
118	25_SS	IS 29425	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Landrace	Qacha's Nek, Lesotho
119	26_SS	IS 2401	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Landrace	Transvaal, South Africa
120	27_SS	IS 30222	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Landrace	Harare, Zimbabwe
121	28_SS	IS 37158	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Landrace	Owambo, Namibia
122	29_SS	IS 13899	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Landrace	KZN, South Africa
123	30_SS	IS 23586	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Landrace	Illubabor, Ethiopia
124	31_SS	IS 35518	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Landrace	Owambo, Namibia
125	33_SS	IS 33065	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Landrace	Tabora, Tanzania
126	34_SS	IS 3574	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Landrace	Kassala, Sudan
127	36_SS	IS 10418	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Breeding line	Uganda
128	37_SS	IS 3804	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Breeding line	Texas, USA
120	38_SS	IS 29200	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Landrace	Mambane, Swaziland
130	39_SS	IS 9444	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Breeding line	Gauteng, South Africa
131	40_SS	IS 23901	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Landrace	Yemen
132	41_SS	IS 2423	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Landrace	Transvaal, South Africa
133	42_SS	IS 9380	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Breeding line	Gauteng, South Africa
134	43_SS	IS 9303	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Breeding line	Gauteng, South Africa

135	44_SS	IS 29413	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Landrace	Swaziland
136	46_SS	IS 13988	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Landrace	KZN, South Africa
137	47_SS	IS 29459	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Landrace	Quthing, Lesotho
138	48_SS	IS 9323	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Advanced line	Gauteng, South Africa
139	49_SS	IS 29243	Zimbabwe	ICRISAT, Matopos	Landrace	Shiselweni, Swaziland
140	2_S	3121	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Landrace	Tsholotsho, Zimbabwe
141	3_S	3088	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Breeding line	
142	4_S	3091	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Breeding line	
143	5_S	3095	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Breeding line	
144	7_S	3143	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Breeding line	
145	8_S	3089	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Breeding line	
146	9_S	1620	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Breeding line	
147	10_S	1338	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Breeding line	
148	11_S	1473	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Breeding line	
149	13_S	3127	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Landrace	Chipinge, Zimbabwe
150	14_S	3116	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Breeding line	
151	16_S	3213	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Breeding line	
152	17_S	3120	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Breeding line	
153	18_S	3207	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Breeding line	
154	19_S	1260	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Breeding line	
155	20_S	1793	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Breeding line	
156	22_S	3079	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Breeding line	
157	23_S	1702	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Breeding line	
158	25_S	1461	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Breeding line	
159	26_S	1761	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Breeding line	
160	27_S	1709	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Breeding line	
161	29_S	1867	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Breeding line	

162	31_S	1256	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Breeding line	
163	32_S	1268	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Breeding line	
164	34_S	3242	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Breeding line	
165	35_S	3135	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Breeding line	
166	36_S	1747	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Breeding line	
167	37_S	1822	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Breeding line	
168	38_S	1629	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Breeding line	
169	39_S	3128	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Breeding line	
170	40_S	1663	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Breeding line	
171	41_S	2031	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Breeding line	
172	42_S	1917	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Breeding line	
173	43_S	3283	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Breeding line	
174	44_S	1605	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Breeding line	
175	47_S	1337	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Breeding line	
176	48_S	1692	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Breeding line	
177	49_S	1160	Zimbabwe	GRBI, Harare	Breeding line	

- BAIL = Bomvitae Agro Industries Limited (BAIL); GRBI = Genetic Resources and Biotechnology Institute;
- The following institutes are constituent institutes of the National Agricultural Research Organisation (NARO) in Uganda - PGRC = Plant Genetic Resource Center; NaLIRRI = National Livestock Resources Research Institute; NaSARRI = National Semi-Arid Resources Research Institute; AbiZARDI = Abi Zonal Agricultural Research and Development Institute.

Table S2: Sorghum genotypes per cluster within the defined Sorghum populations

Cluster	List of sorghum genotypes belonging to the same cluster								
1	43_SS 630B	Sb 3040 388 (65)	ABJ2220-T10 ABJ_2406	23_S	R2X	ABJ2234	ABJ2225-T15	ABJ2244-T39	34_SS
2	UNGB1576 UNGB2890 ABJ2233-T23 Lawera2	UNGB2884 Sb 3038 UNGB3015 152(6)	UNGB2986 132 (5) UNGB2901	138 UNGB2318 UNGB2894	UNGB2830 UNGB2796 Sb3041_15	Lawera UNGB2730 126(3)	UNGB2777 UNGB2314 UNGB2866	Abi 2 UNGB2888 85	Abi 9 Abi 12 UNGB2688
3	36_S Rus 008	13_S 5_S	UNGB2898 49_S	UNGB98 29_SS	13_SS	39_S	22_SS	UNGB2744	UNGB115
4	263 (54) 381 (61) 304 (29)	355 (49)X 323 (37) ABJ 2405	225 (19) SMT2063#20 356	331 (40) 359 (52) 343 (45)W	JK 362 (54)B Sb 3045	G1 126 (3) 396 (68)	236 (15) 352 Taurus	186 (1) 20X 630_T3 SB 39_5(x)108	385 124_B100 20X630_F3
5	24_SS NAROSORG 4	UNGB1574 SESO 3	379 (60)G 398	Abi 13 37_S	38_S Abi 3	43_S NAROSORG2	12_SS	Sb 3039	426 (82)
6	Rus 001 250 (18)A Temani-16H 32_S	UNGB 2674 7_S Sb 3036 Sb 3037	41_SS 41_S Sb 3041	7_SS 27_S 271 (23)	8_S 46_SS 42_S	3_S 14_S 20_S	44_SS 39_SS 19_S	NAROSORG3 18_S 29_S	PAC 501 44_S 3_SS
7	36_SS 37_SS 33_SS 9_SS 10_S	8_SS 26_SS 15_SS 4_SS 47_SS	40_S 27_SS 25_S 2_SS 18_SS_Local	40_SS 21_SS 17_SS 49_SS 1_SS	30_SS 27_SS 5_SS 11_SS 31_S	4_S 21_SS 2_S 6_SS	42_SS 10_SS 31_SS 19_SS	India_23_SS 28_SS 17_S 22_S	20_SS 14_SS 47_S 48_SS
8	26_S	35_S	16_S	38_SS	34_S	48_S	25_SS	11_S	9_S

Figure S1: Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) plot revealing optimal number of clusters (K value). The lowest BIC value was observed at K=8, suggesting the sorghum structure comprised eight subpopulations.